

Machine Learning in Logistics Industry (Capturing Customers Feedback in Large Computing Courses: A Sentiment Analysis Approach)

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Abstract: This study discusses an aspect-based Sentiment Analysis (SA) system for courier services. The suggestion system analyzes the overall sentiment conveyed in a sentence and assigns a unique sentiment to each individual sentence component. The Vader tool and NLP is typically recommended by this study to categorize customer attitudes toward the courier service. This essay provides a summary of sentiment analysis, including its fundamental functions and the most recent approaches created to deal with the difficulties of working with emotionally charged text.

Keywords—Sentimental Analysis, NLP, flask, Vader

I. INTRODUCTION

The courier service industry has recently made excellent success. Given the rising need for delivery services from the general public, this type of business is profitable. From local deliveries to regional, national, and worldwide services, courier services are available on all scales. But society needs to be careful about the decisions it makes.

In summary, this study advises using the Vader tool and NLP to group customer reviews of the services into categories before performing sentiment analysis on the comments from customers. The results of this study should reveal how clients view any courier service problems. The firm can use the knowledge it has gathered to develop customer relationship management in order to better control the market and personalize offerings to clients.

II. METHODOLOGY

The first step of this study's data collection process is document data collection via review data crawling. Preprocessing text is then used to get the data set ready for processing. The next feature uses the Vader tool NLP to analyze the positive, negative, and neutral words. and demonstrate the review's overall positivity.

II.a. Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Machine learning is the foundation of NLP approaches. NLP is specifically used to convert human languages into other languages and interpret human language by machines. This is accomplished with the aid of a few learning guidelines. In NLP, there are several algorithms as well as word databases with their entire forms, definitions, and spelling checks. NLP has made sentiment analysis simpler, which makes it easier to analyze reviews or any other human-provided information.

Figure. 1

II.b. Data Collecting

Create a structure and a style for the content of your essay using the template. Please adhere to the suggested text fonts, column widths, and margins. You might notice anomalies. The head margin, for instance, is substantially larger than typical in this design. This measurement, along with others, is done on purpose. They adhere to rules that presumptively assume your work will be a part of the entire process and not stand alone. Please don't change any of the current names.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

The sentiment analysis in the paper [1] uses the Vader tool, which yields incredibly accurate findings. It has been shown that this feedback gives teachers a valuable opportunity to reflect on their own teaching strategies and course materials in addition to providing them with important information on how students learn.

The use of non-English languages for sentiment analysis is one of the main issues with natural language processing, according to the research [2]. In this paper, we describe a simple but efficient algorithm that delivers precise results when immediately assessing the sentiment of the comments in non-English languages.

Through comments and evaluations, the work generates a large amount of unstructured data points [3]. Unfortunately, unstructured data analytics are more

challenging. placing various points of view in a database that is structured, then using that to look at how individuals respond. Examining and locating the emotions that underlie other people's perspectives on various subjects is the aim of sentiment analysis.

In the era of big data, mining the emotional tendency of comments through artificial intelligence technology is helpful for the timely understanding of network public opinion[4]. In this paper, an improved word representation method is proposed which integrates the contribution of sentiment information into the traditional vader tool and generates weighted word vectors.

Any opinion of an individual through which the feelings, attitudes and thoughts can be expressed is known as sentiment[5]. The reviews of individuals towards certain events, brands, products or companies can be known through sentiment analysis.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

IV.a Pre-processing

The facts extracted from courier evaluation are exceptionally unstructured facts, it must be wiped clean and organized first earlier than analyzing it. Preprocessing the facts includes many tasks. In our case we're fascinated by textual content handiest.

As evaluation extracted from the dataset that we're using to examine sentiment of it are in an unstructured manner. This information contains data such as a few unusual symbols and characters that no longer convey any meaning that machines cannot comprehend. All of this evaluation content includes tools for sentiment analysis. To examine sentiment we required handiest textual content from evaluation and facts. So all this are carried out in pre-processing in which unique symbols and characters are eliminated from review and last textual content are used to examine sentiment. Review also include a few uppercase words and a few phrases that are repeated. This repetition of phrases is removed during pre-processing, capitalized words are changed to lower case, and spelling errors are also fixed for some phrases written in abbreviated form that only people can understand the meaning of, such as "Gm," which stands for "Good Morning," and which contains spelling errors like "good" to "good" to make it easier to understand the sentiment of reviews. After processing is complete, personal opinion sentiment is examined using the continuous review method.

IV.b Data Cleaning

The text needs to be cleaned up and prepped before being analyzed because it is so heavily unstructured. Numerous tasks are involved in data cleaning. In this instance, we are solely concerned with text. We took the text from the review and turned it to a data frame. We also eliminated URLs, stopped words like "the," "a," and "to," superfluous spaces, digits, punctuation, and changed the encoding from latin1 to ASCII. The analysis is carried out after the text has been cleaned up and extra symbols have been removed.

IV.c Special Character and Symbols Removal

At this point, special symbols and characters like (#, *, /, \$, https://, www) are eliminated because they have not convey any sense, and the only text we needed for analysis.

IV.d Numbers removal

The goal at this point is to remove numbers from reviews because they have no significance or value in the field of sentiment analysis. At this stage numbers are taken out of consideration.

IV.e Stop Word removal

In a sentence there are several words that indicate that the meaning of the word is less meaningful. Stop words are those words which are fixed in language like (a, the, an..) such words are removed from review.

```
processed_doc1 = ' '.join([i for i in net_txt.split() if i not in stop_words])
```

IV.f Sentiment score

After processing and cleaning, all that is left is the review' text. Each word in this review is taken one at a time, and then it is compared to a WordNet word using the Vader lexicon tool in the NLTK library of Python. WordNet is a database of words that includes the meaning of each word and its sentimental weight. That word value is provided by the Lexicon Vader tool from WordNet. The sentiment score of review is determined by the value of each word. Once we obtain a sentiment score, we categorize each review as positive, natural, or negative using machine learning.

```
sa = SentimentIntensityAnalyzer()
dd = sa.polarity_scores(text=processed_doc1)
compound = round((1 + dd['compound']) / 2, 2)
percent = compound * 100
```

V. GENERAL DESIGN

In this project, we create a sentiment analysis that accurately identifies users' emotions. It has the ability to analyze a lot of feedback data. The Python modules Vader and Flask were used to build this project. The Vader sentiment can carry out operations based on natural language, like sentiment analysis. The Vedar tool is used to categorize the sentiment into positive, negative, and neutral Prerequisites

- **Flask:** Python-based Flask is a microweb framework. As a micro framework, it is distinguished by not requiring particular software or libraries. It lacks the database abstraction layer, form validation, and other components that are already present and need third-party libraries to do common tasks.
- **Sklearn:** Scikit-learn is a free machine learning library for Python. It supports a variety of techniques, including support vector machines, random forests, and k-neighbors, as well as Python's NumPy and SciPy libraries.
- **Requests:** During a request, the request context keeps track of the request-level data. The request and session proxies are consulted rather than sending the request object to each function that is called during a

request.

- **NLTK:** We are utilizing approaches and techniques for natural language processing. In order to analyze sentiment, we are utilizing the NLTK 2.0.4-powered categorization process for text. A user types emoticons, punctuation, and acronyms in comments on a review panel to convey feelings about them. Our objective is to simply dissect the review in order to determine their opinion about our service. We view reviews as capturing the opinions of individuals and organizations. The core pay attention to factors like the number of positive, negative, and neutral words.
- **VaderSentiment:** The sentiment analysis tool VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner), which is lexicon- and rule-based, is specifically tailored to the sentiments posted on social media. A list of lexical elements (such as words) that are frequently classified as having a positive or negative semantic orientation is known as a sentiment lexicon. VADER makes use of a mix of these. VADER provides us with information about each score's sentimentality in addition to its positivity and negative scores.

Figure.5

```

1 from flask import url_for, redirect
2 from flask import Flask, request, render_template
3 from vaderSentiment.vaderSentiment import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer
4 from flask_wtf import FlaskForm
5 import wtforms
6 import re
7 from nltk.corpus import stopwords
8
9 class FeedbackForm(FlaskForm):
10     feedback = wtforms.TextAreaField('Feedback')
11
12 class FeedbackController:
13     def __init__(self, app):
14         self.app = app
15         self.sia = SentimentIntensityAnalyzer()
16         self.stopwords = stopwords.words('english')
17
18     def index(self):
19         return render_template("form.html")
20
21     def submit(self):
22         form = FeedbackForm(request.form)
23         if form.validate():
24             feedback = form.feedback.data
25             sentiment = self.sia.polarity_scores(feedback)
26             return render_template("result.html", sentiment=sentiment)
27         return redirect(url_for("index"))
28
29 app = Flask(__name__)
30 app.config['SECRET_KEY'] = 'secret'
31 app.config['MYSQL_DATABASE_HOST'] = 'localhost'
32 app.config['MYSQL_DATABASE_USER'] = 'root'
33 app.config['MYSQL_DATABASE_PASSWORD'] = ''
34 app.config['MYSQL_DATABASE'] = 'feedback'
35 mysql = MySQL(app)
36
37 @app.route("/")
38 def index():
39     return FeedbackController(app).index()
40
41 @app.route("/submit")
42 def submit():
43     return FeedbackController(app).submit()
44
45 if __name__ == "__main__":
46     app.run(debug=True)

```

Figure.6

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure.2

Figure.3

Sentiment analysis is a tool designed to help in decision-making by analyzing consumer sentiment. A tool for sentiment analysis that enables individuals to base decisions on the opinions of others regarding a product. It aids businesses in determining what their clients want, considers their offerings and contributes to the development of the finest plans for meeting client needs and delivering the best services. We analyze the sentiment of review data using natural language processing and categorize it as positive, negative, or neutral sentiment. In order to depict sentiment analysis on a web portal, we used the Python flask framework.

VII. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to enhance the previous team's concept and demonstrate that the Vader tool and NLP can accurately execute live sentiment analysis and spelling correction of feedback. It is hoped that a subsequent study would go even farther and develop a mobile software that can analyze text data quickly and effectively in any language and make it available for download on the Apple and Android platforms.

VIII. REFERENCE

[1] "Sentiment Analysis of Text Feedback" Harshal Pandharinath Patil, Arun Parekh, Rajendra Tejaswini, Punam Patil
 [2] "Sentiment Analysis" Manika Lamba, Madhusudan Margam

- [3] “Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis” Prachi Chavan, Sneha Bohra
- [4] “Conducting sentiment analysis” Muhammad Afzaal
- [5] “Sentiment Analysis of Text Feedback” A.Ospanova
- [6] B. Pang, and L. Lee, “Opinion mining and sentiment analysis,” 2nd workshop on making sense of Microposts. Ithaca: Cornell University. Vol.2(1), 2008.
- [7] A. Blom and S. Thorsen, “Automatic Twitter replies with Python,” International conference “Dialog 2012”
- [8] Priyanka Tyagi, R.C. Tripathi “A Review towards the Sentiment Analysis Techniques for the Analysis of Twitter Data”
- [9] Nhan Cach Dang “Sentiment Analysis Based on Deep Learning: A Comparative Study”